

Editor's Message

Dear Readers,

We are truly honoured to edit the special issue of Indian Economic Journal.

With immense gratitude and fortitude we welcome you to the special edition of our conference journal, dedicated to the theme of “Corporate Social Responsibility and Sustainable Development Goals for Vision Viksit Bharat @ 2047”. The papers selected for this issue were presented during the Two Days National Seminar on Corporate Social Responsibility and Sustainable Development Goals for Vision Viksit Bharat @ 2047 held on 14-15th February, 2025 at the University of Lucknow. The Indian Council of Social Science Research had sponsored the national seminar which was organized by the Department of Economics.

Since implementation of Companies' Act, 2014, CSR plays a vital role in shaping the trajectory of India's growth by channelling corporate resources, innovation and expertise toward addressing key developmental challenges. India is supposed to meet the 17 sustainable development goals by 2030. The convergence of CSR and SDGs creates an opportunity to steer India toward long-term development targets while meeting global sustainability standards. India's vision of 'Viksit Bharat' to be achieved by 2047, aims to transform India into a developed nation by 2047, with a strong focus on sustainable development, encompassing economic growth, social progress, environmental sustainability, and good governance.

The themes of the seminar were: (i) CSR Strengthening Education and Skill Development, (ii) Future of CSR in India toward Viksit Bharat @2047, (iii) Role of CSR in achieving SDGs, (iv) Synergies between CSR activities and SDGs, (v) Strategic Alignment of CSR with SDGs, (vi) CSR for Inclusive Growth and Poverty Alleviation, (vii) Transparency, Accountability, and Impact Assessment, (viii) Future of CSR legislation in India, (ix) Monitoring and Accountability in CSR, (x) Opportunities and Challenges in implementing CSR.

The Indian Economic Journal (IEJ) is an important organ of the Indian Economic Association that provides support and services to professionals and researchers both in India and overseas. For over a century, the Indian Economic Association has been one of the largest and the oldest body of teachers, researchers, academicians and policy makers drawn from the background of Economics and allied social sciences. Founded in 1917, the IEA is a 'not for profit, non-political and scholarly voluntary professional association with membership open to those who fulfil the eligibility criteria laid by the constitution of IEA. Through regular outreach programs like 'Conferences, Courses, Publications and Seminars' the IEA disseminates information among scholars to increase the their

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understanding of economics. Both IEJ and IEA work in tandem encouraging members to share their research work findings and contribute scholarly articles in Annual Conferences and for publishing in special edition of IEJ by maintaining relevance.

Our special thanks and gratitude to the Patron of the Seminar, Prof. Alok K Rai, Honourable Vice Chancellor of Lucknow University who meticulously guided us in organizing the seminar on 14-15 February, 2025. Our special thanks to the Association President Prof. Tapan Kumar Shandilya for his valuable contribution. Our heartfelt gratitude to Dr. Anil Kumar Thakur who guided us and facilitated the publication of this issue. Our gratitude to Prof. Devendra Awasthi, Vice President of IEA, who graced the occasion and provided a holistic background of contributions of IEA to the academia world. The national seminar was conducted to collect ideas and policy solutions on how CSR can help the country achieve SDGs for a developing country like India. The seminar was held under the aegis of the ICSSR sponsored project which was headed by the Project Director Dr. Shachi Rai. We would like to thank all the authors and co-authors for the scholarly article contributions for the special issue.

We also express our deepest gratitude to the editorial team that was fully engaged and contributed to the success of the seminar and the seminar volumes. We would like to thank Dr. Harnam Singh, Dr. Parul Jain, Dr. Hemlata Saini, Prof. Roli Misra and all the faculty of the Department of Economics at University of Lucknow. We would like to thank Prof. Vinod Singh, Head of the Department of Economics and Prof. Arvind Mohan, Dean of Faculty of Arts at Lucknow University who took out their precious time and wholeheartedly contributed towards this success. We would also like to thank all the authors, reviewers and the editorial support team, especially the services extended by Mr. Ankit Kumar and Mr. Amarendra Pratap Singh.

Prof. Ravindra K Brahme
Prof. Bharti Pandey
Dr. Shachi Rai

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Role of CSR in Achieving SDGs: The Case of Poverty Reduction and Gender Equality

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Abstract

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) plays a crucial role in addressing key social challenges in India, particularly in poverty reduction, gender equity, and thereby advancement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This paper examines the transformative potential of CSR as a strategic tool for promoting social change, focusing on its impact within sectors such as education, healthcare, and women empowerment. The analysis reveals a significant upward trend in CSR spending, underscoring a growing corporate commitment to social issues. Despite the overall increase in CSR investments, challenges remain, such as the need for improved transparency and genuine community engagement. Furthermore, while targeted initiatives for gender equality and women empowerment have seen notable growth, they still represent a small fraction of total CSR spending. By critically assessing the current landscape and positing actionable recommendations for more effective CSR strategies, this research highlights the necessity of aligning corporate initiatives with the pressing needs of the community to foster inclusive growth and sustainable development in India (SDGs). The findings advocate for a collaborative approach among businesses, government, and civil society to leverage CSR as a vehicle for lasting social progress.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, Gender Equality, Women's Empowerment, Poverty Alleviation, Sustainable Development of India.

1. INTRODUCTION

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has become a key driver of social development in India, complementing government efforts. Rooted in Indian values, it reflects the belief that businesses have a moral duty toward societal welfare. Mahatma Gandhi's idea of trusteeship in 1909 laid the foundation for this vision.

Section 135 of the Companies Act, 2013 mandates certain companies to spend a portion of their profits on CSR and report their activities. The law aims to enhance accountability and align business with social and environmental goals. However, implementation faces challenges like limited transparency, weak community engagement,

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and superficial compliance. Many companies focus on fulfilling legal requirements rather than creating meaningful impact.

In this context, CSR holds immense potential as a tool for driving positive societal change. When companies strategically align their CSR initiatives with the critical needs of the community, they can play a vital role in alleviating poverty, advancing gender equity, and furthering the global agenda for sustainable development.

To drive sustainable development, India must refine its CSR strategies through collaborative efforts among businesses, government, NGOs, and communities. Such partnerships enhance the effectiveness of CSR initiatives. This approach helps address key issues like poverty, gender equity, and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

CSR has been widely recognized as a key mechanism for addressing socio-economic challenges like poverty, gender equity, and sustainable development. Kaur and Sharma (2019) and Kapoor and Srivastava (2017) emphasized CSR's role in poverty alleviation in India, while Ahmed and Hassan (2015) and Kumar and Singh (2018) highlighted its impact on gender equity. The United Nations (2015) and Bhattacharya and Sen (2013) further stressed CSR's importance in achieving the SDGs through inclusive and sustainable practices.

3. OBJECTIVES

1. To analyze the trends in CSR spending across various developmental sectors in India.
2. To assess the impact of CSR initiatives on poverty reduction and gender equality.
3. To identify the top corporate contributors to social development.
4. To explore how CSR aligns with the SDGs.

4. HYPOTHESIS

1. Increased CSR spending positively correlates with reductions in poverty levels in India.
2. Companies with dedicated CSR programs for gender equality will see improved employee productivity.
3. Higher levels of transparency in CSR reporting led to increased community engagement.
4. Significant investment in women's empowerment initiatives correlates to improved socio-economic outcomes.
5. The shift in CSR focus towards targeted gender issues reflects broader societal changes in India.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research adopts a mixed-methods approach, analyzing CSR spending trends using quantitative data from fiscal reports and qualitative case studies of successful gender-focused initiatives. Data is drawn from government sources, corporate disclosures, and third-party

studies. Trend and thematic analyses are used to identify patterns and best practices, with the goal of offering actionable recommendations for businesses and policymakers.

6. ANALYTICAL STUDY

6.1 CSR

Under the Companies Act, 2013, companies with an annual turnover of ₹ 1,000 crore or more, a net worth of ₹ 500 crore or more, or a net profit of ₹ 5 crore or more are subject to corporate social responsibility (CSR) regulations. Such companies are required to establish a CSR committee and are encouraged to spend 2% of their average net profit from the preceding three years on CSR activities. There are several areas under CSR where companies can actively play their role:

6.1.1. Social Development

Education plays a crucial role not only for individual growth but also for societal advancement, and companies can significantly contribute to this by engaging in various educational initiatives. Their involvement can span from primary education to higher education through activities such as offering scholarships, establishing schools, supporting essential infrastructure, and training teachers. Additionally, in the realm of health and wellness, companies have the opportunity to enhance healthcare services by organizing free health camps, distributing medicines, conducting mental health workshops, and running awareness campaigns. These efforts collectively promote healthier lifestyles and foster overall community well-being.

6.1.2. Environmental Protection

Under green policies, companies can focus on programs such as energy conservation, recycling, and waste management. Various activities aimed at reducing water, air, and soil pollution are crucial, including tree plantation drives, pollution control technologies, and sustainable agriculture.

6.1.3. Economic Development

To ensure economic development, companies can encourage small and medium enterprises. This can be achieved by providing financial assistance, technical knowledge, and resource availability to local enterprises. Such initiatives not only empower the local economy but also create job opportunities.

6.1.4. Gender Equality and Women Empowerment

Promoting gender equality is an important direction of CSR. Companies undertake significant work in this direction by promoting women entrepreneurship, organizing thrift and support programs for working women, and conducting awareness programs against violence towards women.

6.1.5. Social Justice and Inclusivity

Companies contribute to social justice and inclusivity by launching programs that

uplift marginalized communities, especially Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes. These initiatives focus on empowering individuals through education and entrepreneurship, fostering workplace diversity, supporting rights-based campaigns, and engaging in community outreach. By prioritizing these efforts, companies not only enhance their brand reputation but also play a crucial role in driving meaningful social change.

6.2 Role of CSR in Poverty Reduction

Poverty is a global problem that poses a significant challenge in many countries, including India. It prevents many people from accessing basic necessities such as education, health, and employment. In this context, CSR can play a crucial role in alleviating poverty. Many companies are making various efforts to provide education, health, and employment opportunities to the poor, while also working in areas such as rural development, women's empowerment, and social awareness. There are several benefits of reducing poverty through CSR; it not only improves the living standards of the poor but also contributes to the overall development of the country. Reducing poverty leads to improvements in economic growth, social stability, and political stability as well. However, CSR faces challenges in addressing poverty, such as the complexity of the issue, which does not have simple solutions, and the need for greater investment and resources that are often not readily available.

CSR in India has seen a significant increase in spending over recent years, reflecting a growing commitment from corporations to contribute to social development, including poverty reduction.

Table 1: CSR Spending

Sl.No.	Financial Year	Total Amount Spent (INR Cr.)
1.	FY 2022-23	29,986.92
2.	FY 2021-22	26,579.78
3.	FY 2020-21	26,210.95
4.	FY 2019-20	24,965.82
5.	FY 2018-19	20,217.65

Source: <https://www.csr.gov.in/content/csr/global/master/home/home.html>

The table illustrates a steady rise in the CSR expenditure from FY 2018-19 to FY 2022-23, with the total amount spent growing from ₹ 20,217.65 crore in FY 2018-19 to ₹ 29,986.92 crore in FY 2022-23, reflecting a notable increase in corporate commitment to social development. While there was a significant jump of approximately 23.4% from FY 2018-19 to FY 2019-20, the growth rate remained steady at 1.4% in FY 2021-22, before accelerating to 13.1% in FY 2022-23. This consistent rise indicates that corporations are prioritizing CSR investments in critical sectors such as healthcare, education, rural development, and environmental sustainability, aligning with broader national development goals.

The top CSR spenders in FY23 include HDFC Bank (₹ 803.15 crore), TCS (₹ 774.44 crore), and RIL (₹ 743.40 crore), followed by ICICI Bank and Tata Steel, with expenditures

Table 2: Top CSR Spenders (FY23)

Sl.No.	Company	Amount (₹ Crore)
1.	HDFC Bank	803.15
2.	TCS	774.44
3.	RIL	743.40
4.	ICICI Bank	476.55
5.	Tata Steel	475.10

Source: CSR Report 2023.

of ₹ 476.55 crore and ₹ 475.10 crore, respectively. These corporations have significantly contributed to various developmental projects, reflecting their commitment to social responsibility and the nation's growth. Their contributions have primarily focused on sectors like education, healthcare, rural development, environmental sustainability, and livelihood enhancement for poverty reduction in India and social empowerment.

Table 3 Captures the CSR spending trends across sectors and top contributors in FY23.

Table : CSR Spending by Sectors (₹ crore)

Sl.No.	Sectors	FY19	FY20	FY21	FY22	FY23
1.	Education	6,117	6,179	6,593	6,957	7,238
2.	Healthcare	3,672	4,905	5,708	6,364	6,830
3.	Rural Development	2,134	2,132	2,182	2,360	2,606
4.	Environmental Sustainability	1,908	1,927	1,960	2,332	3,061
5.	Livelihood Enhancement	1,654	1,745	1,854	1,983	2,154

Source: Ministry of Corporate Affairs. (2023). *CSR Spending Trends across Sectors: FY19-FY23*.

CSR spending by sectors reveals education and healthcare as the highest-funded areas, with ₹ 7,238 crore and ₹ 6,830 crore allocated in FY23, respectively. Other sectors like rural development (₹ 2,606 crore), environmental sustainability (₹ 3,061 crore), and livelihood enhancement (₹ 2,154 crore) also witnessed growth over the years. This steady increase across all sectors highlights a consistent effort to address key social and environmental issues, showcasing the strategic role of CSR in fostering inclusive and sustainable development.

6.3 Promoting Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment Through CSR in India

Gender-inclusive workplaces enhance productivity, foster responsible leadership, and contribute to broader social welfare. Organizations with women in top management often outperform those without, while inclusive leadership drives humanitarian and environmental responsibility. Major Indian companies—such as Reliance, SBI, Hero Motocorp, TCS, and HDFC Bank—are actively promoting women's empowerment through CSR programs focused on digital literacy, entrepreneurship, health, and education. Though only 1.5% of CSR funds were directed toward gender equality from 2014 to 2021, the sharp increase to ₹ 97.86 crore in 2021-22 marks a growing recognition of the need to address gender disparities and promote inclusive growth.

Table 4: CSR Investments in Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment (2014-2022)

Sl.No.	Financial Year	Gender Equality (₹ Crore)	Women Empowerment (₹ Crore)
1.	2014-15	55.21	72.87
2.	2015-16	73.85	122.79
3.	2016-17	72.60	163.46
4.	2017-18	24.01	251.37
5.	2018-19	51.86	236.54
6.	2019-20	82.93	259.57
7.	2020-21	43.83	206.00
8.	2021-22	97.86	253.86

Source: CSR Spending, India CSR Report (2014-2022).

This data reflects a fluctuating yet overall increasing trend in CSR allocations towards gender-focused initiatives, underscoring the evolving role of corporate contributions in promoting gender equality in India.

Table 5: CSR Expenditure on Development Sectors (2020-2022)

Sl.No.	Development Sector	CSR Spend 2020-2021 (in crores)	CSR Spend 2021-2022 (in crores)
1	Women Empowerment	206	253.86
2	Education	6693.25	6482.72
3	Gender Equality	43.83	97.86
4	Socio-Economic Inequalities	149.81	161.72

Source: CSR Spending, India CSR Report (2020-2022).

The table shows CSR spending across various sectors for 2020-2021 and 2021-2022, revealing an increase in investments in women's empowerment (from ₹ 206 crores to ₹ 253.86 crores) and gender equality (from ₹ 43.83 crores to ₹ 97.86 crores), indicating a growing corporate focus on gender disparities. Education spending, while still the highest, declined slightly from ₹ 6,693.25 crores to ₹ 6,482.72 crores, possibly due to the completion of major projects. Investments in socio-economic inequalities rose moderately from ₹ 149.81 crores to ₹ 161.72 crores. Overall, these trends point to a shift towards targeted initiatives in gender issues and socio-economic development, reflecting broader societal priorities.

Table 6 lists the companies that have contributed to the development of gender equality and women empowerment initiatives through their CSR efforts, along with the financial commitment made by each company towards this cause.

The companies listed have made significant CSR contributions towards gender equality and women empowerment, with a focus on areas like digital literacy, healthcare, education, and skill development. Their financial support, ranging from INR 0.9 Cr. to INR 1.87 Cr., helps empower women, reduce inequalities, and promote inclusivity across various sectors, fostering a more equitable society.

Table 6: CSR Contributions in Gender Equality Sector

Sl.No.	Company Name(s)	Amount (INR Cr.)
1.	Microsoft Corporation (India) Pvt Ltd.	1.87
2.	Ericsson India Private Limited	1.66
3.	Aculife Healthcare Private Limited	1.25
4.	Hindalco Industries Limited	1.25
5.	Sangam (India) Limited	1.2
6.	Sjvn Limited	1.13
7.	Cummins India Limited	1.05
8.	Mahindra Susten Private Limited	0.96
9.	United Breweries Limited	0.91
10.	Culver Max Entertainment Private Limited	0.9

Source: CSR Report form National Portal of India.

CONCLUSION

CSR plays a vital role in addressing key challenges like poverty, gender equity, and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in India. This paper highlights how strategically designed CSR initiatives, especially those focusing on women's empowerment, can drive meaningful social and economic progress. While CSR spending and corporate engagement have grown, challenges such as limited transparency and community involvement persist. Strengthening collaboration among businesses, governments, and civil society will be essential to making CSR a more impactful tool for inclusive and sustainable development.

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